

Title	Report on identifying the optimal cost model and pricing schemes for distributed Research Infrastructures
Work package n°	1
Deliverable n°	3
Lead beneficiary	CNRS
Author(s)	Sabine Philippin (CNRS), Matilde Oliveri (CNRS), Ariane Dubost (CNRS), Zhuoqun Wu (CNRS)
Deliverable Type	R
Dissemination Level	PU
Estimated delivery date	July 2024 (M40)
Actual delivery date	June 16 2025 (M51)
Version	1
Reviewed by	Paolo Laj
Accepted by	
Comments	

Abstract

Sustainable access to Research Infrastructures (RIs) is essential for fostering scientific innovation and collaboration. This document examines financial frameworks and cost models for access to distributed atmospheric RIs, emphasizing the balance between affordability and sustainability. The study outlines a diversified funding strategy combining diverse funding sources. A comprehensive unit cost analysis allows to estimate the required resources needed for ensuring broad access. The findings support the development of equitable, transparent pricing schemes tailored to user categories and service types that ensure long-term financial viability while preserving accessibility and research excellence.

List of common acronyms used in this document

Acronym	Definition
ASC	Atmospheric Simulation Chamber
CL	Central Laboratory, European-level RI facility
DAY	Unit of access, measured in days, independent of the number of users
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
INFRA-SERV	European grant funding supporting transnational and virtual access to infrastructure services
MOB	Mobile platform/facility
OBS	Observational platform/facility
PA	Physical access
RA	Remote access
RI	Research Infrastructure
SWD	Unit of access, measured in Staff-Working-Day
UWD	Unit of access, measured in User-Working-Day
TNA	Transnational Access
VA	Virtual Access

1	Introduction	5
2	Funding framework and objectives	6
2.1	Diversity of funding sources	7
2.2	Funding framework of distributed European RIs for access provision	10
3	Process and challenges	11
3.1	Planned process for developing a sustainable pricing scheme	12
3.2	Access cost collector tool	15
3.3	Difficulties encountered	15
4	Analysis of results	16
4.1	Variable cost fraction and/or ATMO-ACCESS TNA unit costs	16
4.2	Resources required for annual access provision	20
5	Principles and pathways for pricing access	25
5.1	Principles for pricing policy	26
5.2	Funding pathways for users	27
6	Conclusions	29
7	Reference documents	30
	Annex A. Overview of European ERICs and access funding	31
	Annex B. Design of the access cost collector tool and guidelines for data collection	39
B.1	Access cost collector tool	39
B.2	Guidelines for data collection using the cost collector tool	41

1 Introduction

Research Infrastructures (RIs) play a critical role in advancing scientific knowledge and fostering innovation by providing high-level services, data, and resources to a wide range of users across disciplines and sectors. Distributed RIs, characterized by their networked structure spanning multiple and different facility types as well as hosting institutions, introduce unique challenges for defining sustainable cost models and pricing schemes for user access.

Sustainable access to RIs refers to ensuring that RI services remain open and available to a wide user community, while maintaining financial viability over the long term. Access refers to the provision of services and resources to external users including researchers, public authorities, private and other actors (it does not refer to RI-internal operational support provided to national nodes or internal RI management activities). RI services may comprise access to data and digital tools, instrumented platforms for scientific and technological usage, training, expertise, and more. Sustainable access requires to consider the diversity of funding sources, user categories, and services, while fostering scientific excellence through competitive and innovative research opportunities. Sustainability also requires implementing a balance between equitable access for a broad user base and an effective pricing strategy.

Adequate access cost models are essential tools in this context, helping to quantify the costs that are associated with providing access to RI services. Cost models define which categories of operational costs will be taken into account for a service pricing scheme. The expenses related to the RI operations for access provision include investment, personnel, consumables, other running costs, and indirect costs, while also distinguishing between fixed costs (general operating costs of a facility) and variable costs (additional costs incurring to access provision). Furthermore, cost models must be flexible enough to accommodate the wide range of services offered by distributed RIs, as well as the different types of access (physical, remote, hybrid, virtual access¹).

To recover the costs for provision of access, pricing options are essential for defining the set of service fees that can be applied to users. A transparent and well-structured pricing policy ensures that access costs are predictable, fair, and aligned with the principles of sustainability

¹ Physical access refers to “hands-on” use of an infrastructure, where users are physically present at a facility, platform, or site. Remote access allows users to utilise resources or services without being physically present on site (e.g., by operating instruments or requesting measurements performed by local staff). Hybrid access combines both physical and remote components within a single access project. In contrast, virtual access refers to the use of digital services and tools through communication networks.

and RIs access and data policies. It should balance affordability for users, with the need to cover the minimum operational expenses for access provision. Differentiated pricing schemes are dependent on the type of user (e.g., standard service fees for industry partners, reduced rates for academic users) and on the type of service (e.g. tailored services). They can support broader accessibility while contributing to financial viability. Ultimately, the pricing policy will play a key role in fostering long-term, sustainable access.

The main objective of ATMO-ACCESS is to develop the concept and guidelines for access to distributed atmospheric research infrastructures. As part of the financial framework in WP1, the aim is to propose guidelines for a suitable funding scheme for access to atmospheric RI services, considered crucial to underpin the sustainability of RIs by drawing from a variety of sources. In the context of national and European Roadmaps, different kinds of funding sources are available. These include national/regional/institutional funding, European or national project funding, user/service fees, as well as RI funding covered by its member countries as part of the RI access programme. Diversified funding sources are complementary and help to reduce reliance on a single source and they also enhance the resilience of the RI's financial model.

This document describes the activities undertaken in the project for identifying the optimal cost model and explore common approaches pricing schemes for distributed RIs, in particular the atmospheric RIs in Europe. We will present the relevant funding frameworks and environment related to distributed RIs, address the different types of facilities and access, and discuss the diversity of funding sources (Section 2). The planned process for developing sustainable pricing schemes and challenges encountered is outlined in Section 3. An analysis of available access cost calculations from facilities involved in ATMO-ACCESS results has been carried out and results are presented (Section 4). Finally, the principles for a robust and balanced pricing strategy are presented in Section 5 along with suggestions for possible funding pathways of user access. The conclusions are presented in Section 6, supported by reference documents that include information on access funding for ERICs (European RI consortia) and examples of access cost calculations (Annexes A, B and C). The detailed cost information provided in Annex C is only available in an internal version of the document (accessible for internal use and by the European Commission).

2 Funding framework and objectives

Long-term sustainability for distributed RIs requires a well-structured and diversified funding strategy for access provision. Particularly physical and remote access are often not covered by

the ERIC funding model and additional funding mechanisms are often needed to support the full range of access services. This involves mobilising various funding sources and aligning them within a coherent framework that support both the operational needs and the scientific RI strategy. The diversity of funding sources is outlined in the following, as well as the funding framework of the distributed European RIs.

2.1 Diversity of funding sources

Achieving long-term sustainability for distributed RIs requires leveraging a diverse range of funding sources and mechanisms for access to its services. The key funding sources include i) **national/regional or institutional funding**, ii) **project funding** (European and national), iii) **RI funding** (through membership contributions), and iv) **other funding** (e.g., user or service fees), as illustrated in Figure 1. These funding sources are further detailed below.

(1) National, regional and institutional funding

National and Regional Funding is primarily provided by government budgets, regional authorities, and public bodies, and may also include institutional funding from research performing organisations (RPOs) and universities. The level of support varies across countries, reflecting national research priorities and scientific programmes, often guided by national roadmaps (where available).

Such funding typically supports the construction and core operations of the national RI nodes, which include scientific and technical installations, facilities, and platforms. It covers essential activities required for the provision of access to their services: maintenance of the facility and instruments, equipment upgrading, covering of staff salaries. This funding ensures the long-term stability and strategic development of the infrastructure, aligned with national or regional research agendas.

Figure 1. Sources for funding of access to RI services.

Additionally, national and regional authorities may also co-fund RIs using EU structural funds, mainly through European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF²). These funds aim to reduce regional disparities across Europe by boosting economic development and innovation, including investments in RIs. Structural funds can support the facilities' research capacity and complement the available national or regional budgets.

(2) Project funding

Project funding primarily comes from competitive grants or calls, such as those under Horizon Europe or national research programmes. This funding typically supports specific research activities including collaborative projects, experimental campaigns, and technology development. For RIs, project-based funding, particularly through the EU INFRA programme, can play a complementary role by supporting specific developments to enhance the RIs' access capabilities. Such funding may contribute to enabling access to external users, develop specialized instruments and methods, or recruiting short-term personnel for targeted activities.

In this context, the EU Framework Programmes (FP) provide a structured research framework dedicated to supporting RIs. Various calls offer funding to facilitate and support the construction, implementation, and strategic development of RIs. The key funding instruments include i) INFRA-DEV for developing, consolidating, and optimizing the European RIs landscape, maintaining global leadership; ii) INFRA-SERV, for RI services to support health research, accelerate the green and digital transformation, and advance frontier knowledge, iii) INFRA-TECH for the next generation of scientific instruments, tools, methods, and advanced digital solutions, iv) INFRA-EOSC to enable an operational, open, and FAIR European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem, as well as v) INFRA-NET for network connectivity to enable collaboration without boundaries. Horizon Europe also offers grants for research and innovation projects, Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions, and European Research Council (ERC) grants, which, although primarily research-focused, may provide opportunities to engage with RIs and make use of their services. Both the public and private sectors users can benefit from these grants, supporting expenses related to travel, accommodation, consumables for experiments conducted at and supported by the RIs.

² Structural funds are jointly managed by the European Commission and national or regional authorities. The funds under [ESIF](https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_23_389) (https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_23_389) include, among others, the European Regional Development Fund ([ERDF](https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/erdf_en), https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/erdf_en) and the Cohesion Fund ([CF](https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/cohesion-fund_en), https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/cohesion-fund_en).

EU funding has been fundamental for developing and funding activities related to transnational access (TNA), which has particularly been important for both physical and remote access, as well as virtual access (VA). The TNA-VA program has played an integral role in creating a more integrated research environment. It has contributed to structuring and streamlining access procedures, improving operational access to distributed RIs' facilities and resources, as well as promoting visibility of RIs and international collaboration. In this way, project funding enhances the accessibility and functionality of RIs, and fosters cross-border collaboration and innovation.

(3) RI funding

The funding of operational RIs relies above all on the contributions of their participating member and observer countries. For RIs structured as legal entities, like ACTRIS ERIC and ICOS ERIC, member countries contribute annual fees based on agreed formulas. This RI funding, while distinct from other funding sources, is essential for covering the RI's core functions. These include central coordination, and European-level thematic facilities, data centres, and scientific and technological developments, training programmes etc.

This funding also supports the provision of data and services, as well as the implementation of long-term strategies. However, such funding typically does not cover the full costs of RI operation, especially in terms of physical, remote or hybrid access provision. RI funding can become vital for implementing a coordinated access programme that ensures equitable access to RI facilities and services. Such programmes enhance operational efficiency by harmonizing access procedures, promoting cross-border collaboration, and creating an inclusive research environment. By fostering a cohesive and well-coordinated network, RI funding strengthens the visibility and impact of RIs, facilitating seamless access for academic, private and societal users. As of today, none of the atmospheric RIs participating in ATMO-ACCESS (ACTRIS ERIC, ICOS ERIC, IAGOS) have implemented a financial model to support physical or remote access based on the countries' membership contributions. However, establishing such a funding model is recognised as a strategic objective, particularly for RIs like ACTRIS ERIC, where many services depend on non-virtual access.

(4) Other funding

Other funding includes **user or service fees** which help cover costs for service provision, associated with facility maintenance, consumables, and technical and scientific support for user-driven activities. Service fees may apply to specific users, such as private sector entities conducting proprietary research, or for specialised services like tailored digital services, analysis tools, consulting etc.

Additional funding may also come from **bilateral agreements** between the RI and specific countries, RPOs (Research Performing Organisations) or user groups. For instance, in the context of the Italian project [ITINERIS](#) (Italian Integrated Environmental Research Infrastructures System), a collaboration agreement with ACTRIS ERIC facilitates transnational access outside the traditional EU TNA schemes. In this particular case it supports access of Italian users to services provided by ACTRIS facilities, while also granting access for users from ACTRIS member countries to services provided by Italian facilities. In parallel, a separate series of contracts with the European Centre for Medium range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) supports the delivery of specific services, namely the near-real-time provision of ACTRIS data to the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service ([CAMS](#)), representing a form of service-oriented funding (rather than access provision).

Although these funding streams typically represent a smaller share of the overall RI budget, they contribute to diversifying revenue sources and fostering long-term sustainability.

2.2 Funding framework of distributed European RIs for access provision

Most distributed RIs in Europe, particularly those operating under the European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) framework, rely on multi-level funding structures, as described in Section 2.1, to sustain operations and ensure user access. Notably, 93% of ERICs are distributed RIs. An overview of the 28 European ERICs and an additional 20 (mostly distributed) RIs investigated is provided in Annex A. Among these ERICs, the majority (71%, or 20 ERICs) provide all types of access including physical, remote, and virtual access, while 19% (eight ERICs) offer virtual access to data and digital services only. Similarly, of the distributed RIs analysed, 75% (15 RIs) provide all types of access, whereas only 15% (five RIs) offer virtual access exclusively. Given our focus on physical/remote access funding, we primarily focus on the financial models supporting such access within these distributed RIs.

ERICs are primarily funded through financial contributions from their member and observer countries, which commit long-term funding based on agreed governance models. These contributions are typically determined by factors such as investment levels, the number of national nodes or facilities included, GDP (Gross Domestic Product) share, or other negotiated fixed or variable fees. This funding ensures the sustainability of central coordination activities, data services, and infrastructure development. However, direct financial support for physical/remote access provision is only explicitly accounted for in a limited number of cases. Very few ERICs incorporate physical/remote access into their financial models, though some do

provide free or subsidized access for users from member countries. Examples of distributed RIs following this model include BBMRI ERIC, CERIC-ERIC, ELI ERIC, Euro-BioImaging ERIC, EU SOLARIS ERIC, INFRAFRONTIER ERIC, INSTRUMENT ERIC, and SIOS.

Since distributed RIs operate through national nodes, participating host institutions secure additional **national funding** from sources such as national research agencies, ministries, universities, or institutional budgets. This funding typically covers personnel, operational costs, and facility maintenance. Some ERICs also benefit from **structural funds** to develop infrastructure capacity in specific regions. National funding often facilitates national access, while some ERICs offer **subsidised access** through bilateral agreements, national programs, or co-funding schemes that partially waive user fees or provide preferential rates for researchers from member countries. ERICs, and particularly non-ERIC RIs, rely heavily on **competitive European Commission (EC) funding** through infrastructure programs such as INFRA-DEV, INFRA-EOSC, INFRA-SERV, and INFRA-TECH. These grants help to enhance services, develop new capabilities, and support transnational (physical/remote access) and virtual access. However, as these grants are temporary and require periodic reapplication, they do not provide a sustainable long-term funding model for access provision. It is important to note that as of today, half of the 26 distributed ERICs have implemented **service fee** models in which users pay for access, particularly in the case of industry users or researchers from non-member states.

The sustainability of distributed RIs depends on a stable combination of funding source. While few distributed ERICs integrate access provision into their financial structures, many still rely on national commitments and continuous access to competitive EU funding programs, highlighting the ongoing challenge of securing long-term funding for access.

3 Process and challenges

During the initial phase of the project, we defined a detailed approach for establishing a sustainable pricing scheme, as detailed below. While the aims were to gather statistically representative material covering access to services from all types of facilities in the project, we encountered certain limitations which are furthermore discussed.

3.1 Planned process for developing a sustainable pricing scheme

ATMO-ACCESS comprises more than 60 diverse facilities for providing access (Figure 2), including:

- **Observational platforms:** ground-based platforms to perform experiments in ambient conditions and to deliver long-term data based on common operation standards;
- **Atmospheric simulation chambers:** highly instrument platforms to perform experiments under controlled laboratory conditions and targeting detailed investigation of atmospheric processes;
- **Mobile platforms:** mobile observation facilities equipped with atmospheric measurement equipment for conducting experiments and campaigns under ambient natural conditions;
- **Central laboratories:** facilities and mobile reference platforms to ensure the production of harmonized, reliable and document data compliant with standard operating procedures and quality protocols;
- **Virtual platforms:** cross-RI, online data and computing platforms provided by atmospheric RI data hubs (ACTRIS DC, ICOS DC, IAGOS DC) as well as cross-RI virtual training platforms.

The aim of the cost analysis is to gather data on access costs from a selected and representative number of different types of facilities participating in the project for the provision of physical, remote and hybrid access (costs related to virtual access are not considered in this exercise).

29 OBSERVATION FACILITIES

14 ATMOSPHERIC SIMULATION CHAMBERS

5 MOBILE PLATFORMS

13 CENTRAL LABORATORIES

VIRTUAL PLATFORMS

Figure 2. ATMO-ACCESS facilities participating in the provision of access and their geographical locations.

The planned process towards a pricing scheme for access to RI services is based on the methodology described in Milestone 30 – Report on access cost studies at selected facilities (R1) and comprises the following four steps (Figure 3):

(1) Comprehensive data collection and cost analysis

A detailed assessment of full access costs at ATMO-ACCESS facilities is conducted using a defined methodology. A comprehensive data collection is a pertinent step in the overall process. An analysis requires a representative dataset encompassing access types, access units, quantity of access provided and user information (e.g., user origin).

(2) Development of access cost models

Based on the collected data, various access cost models are formulated, taking into account different cost categories: investment costs, personnel costs, other operational costs, and indirect costs. A key aspect of this step is distinguishing between the variable

and fixed fraction of access costs. The access cost model aligns with the relevant unit to be representative for the unit cost estimations.

(3) Design of pricing options

Multiple pricing options are defined to establish a structured fee system. These options consider factors such as user type and the specific services utilized, ensuring a fair and adaptable pricing structure.

(4) Assessing financial mechanisms

Various funding sources (national/regional/institutional funding, project-based funding, RI funding, and other potential financial contributions) are assessed to identify sustainable mechanisms for covering access costs.

Figure 3. Initially planned process for developing a sustainable RI pricing scheme

The initially planned process aimed at providing a comprehensive understanding of the cost structure and ensures that pricing decisions are based on well-informed financial insights. This intended a **full cost exercise**, although knowing that some costs would not directly be included in the access and pricing model (e.g., investment costs, fixed operations costs). The full cost analysis is considered essential as explained in the following:

- A full cost analysis helps identify all cost components and, therefore, the true costs of access. Even if fixed costs are not factored into pricing, knowing their magnitude helps in financial planning and sustainability.
- A distinction of fixed vs variable costs allows for a more precise calculation of the real operational cost for access provision.
- While fixed costs may not be charged directly to users, users should be aware of the full costs of access. Importantly, these fixed costs still need to be covered through other funding mechanisms (e.g., national, institutional budgets, grants etc.). A full cost exercise ensures that hidden or underestimated costs do not lead to financial gaps.
- Even if the initial pricing model may exclude fixed costs, having a full cost breakdown allows may be relevant for future pricing revisions. A full cost analysis furthermore provides transparency in financial reporting and strengthens justifications when applying for funding support to cover the fixed fraction of access costs.

3.2 Access cost collector tool

An access cost collector tool has been developed for collecting the full costs of the facility operations. Extracts of the tool design of the tool are illustrated in annex B.1. The aim was to collect information from a representative number of the different type of facilities (observational platforms, atmospheric simulation chambers, mobile platforms, central laboratories), the different cost categories (personnel, other, equipment, indirect costs), different types of costs (fixed, variable costs), and other relevant information including the access unit used, the access type (physical vs remote access), and the quantity of access provided (international, national, internal access) for a representative period of time (at least two years). The typical access units depend on the facility type and comprise user-working-day (generally used at observational facilities), day (for simulation chambers), or staff-working-time (very useful to facilitate the application of an access unit to both types of access physical and remote). The details of the access unit are described in the guidelines for use of the collector tool (see Annex B.2).

3.3 Difficulties encountered

Despite continuous interaction and support from WP1, providing full cost data through the access cost collector tool proved to be a complex task for the access providers. Challenges arose

in particular for two aspects: i) compiling a comprehensive equipment list and determining which instrument to include and how to account for their depreciation; and ii) distinguishing between fixed and variable cost for each of cost item, based on best judgment, as the information is generally not tracked.

To ensure representativity in determining unit costs for each facility, the data collection was designed to cover at least a full two-year period. However, this proved particularly difficult, as the years concerned were impacted by the pandemic (2020-2023). The pandemic not only significantly reduced the access activities (as the mobility of users was impacted) but also disrupted overall facility operations. As a result, providers were hesitant to use these data, considering them unrepresentative of typical facility operations.

Additionally, conducting a full cost exercise is inherently rather time-consuming. Given these circumstances, additionally to the constraints related to equipment data, to separating fixed vs variable costs, and the representative reference period, the collection of detailed and comprehensive data from a large number of facilities was particularly challenging.

Ultimately, 11 ATMO-ACCESS facilities participated in the exercise, including four observational platforms and seven atmospheric simulation chambers.

4 Analysis of results

4.1 Variable cost fraction and/or ATMO-ACCESS TNA unit costs

A summary of the collected access costs is presented in Table 1, with detailed data available in Annex C.1-11. The following parameters have been derived from the data: the variable fraction of the access costs (i.e., the costs directly associated with providing access, excluding fixed operational costs, both with and without equipment), the calculated unit cost (based on total costs and the total quantity of access provided, both with and without equipment), the TNA unit cost as initially calculated for the ATMO-ACCESS project, the variable fraction of the unit cost without equipment, and the resources required for the transnational access, based on the variable fraction without equipment.

On average, across the 11 facilities, the variable fraction of access costs represents 36%, with little difference when including or excluding equipment costs. However, the data are highly heterogeneous, with the variable fraction ranging from 11% to 81%. Generally, the variable fraction of the unit costs is higher for simulation chambers (43% on average) than for

observational platforms (24% on average). This is expected, as the operations of the observational platforms are significantly less impacted by service provision compared to simulation chambers. While access-related activities account for the full operation of simulation chambers during access periods, observational platforms can typically continue their measurement programs in parallel.

A comparison between the variable fraction of the unit costs (without equipment) and the ATMO-ACCESS unit cost reveals a positive linear relationship (Figure 4). Although some data uncertainties, a proportionality can be inferred, given a slope of 1.05, while a variation of 24% remains unexplained ($R^2=0.76$). Three facilities are excluded in the graph, as their access costs within the project are based on actual expenditures for access provision, and no unit cost is available for comparison.

Figure 4. Comparison of unit costs between collected variable fraction of access costs (without equipment) and the ATMO-ACCESS unit costs.

In the absence of representative data from the access cost collection, it is unfortunately not possible to propose different cost models that account for various cost categories.

However, based on the above finding, the unit cost derived from the TNA calculation serves as first approximation and may be used in cases when data on the variable fraction from the cost collector are unavailable. This model includes personnel and other costs but excludes

ATMO ACCESS
Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

equipment or infrastructure costs. Once more detailed access cost data are collected and available, additional cost models can be explored.

Table 1. Summary of access costs collected, indicated furthermore is the quantity of access considered for the unit cost calculations as well as the access unit (Day: one day, independent on the number of users, UWD: one user-working day, SWD: one staff-working-day).

Facility	Type	Variable fraction with Equipment costs	Variable fraction without Equipment costs	Total unit cost w/o Equipment costs	Variable unit cost w/o Equipment costs	ATMO-ACCESS Unit cost (total costs)	Variable unit cost w/o Equipment costs vs ATMO unit cost	Resources for EU / Int access per year (variable fraction, w/o Equ)	Quantity of access considered	Unit of access
CESAM	ASC	57%	64%	3 399 €	2 161 €	2 100 €	103%	79 947 €	37	Days
AURA	ASC	68%	63%	324 €	206 €	n/a (actual)		514 €	2,5	Days
ChAMBRe	ASC	34%	33%	13 132 €	4 220 €	n/a (actual)		12 660 €	3	Days
EUPHORE	ASC	39%	42%	6 326 €	2 671 €	3 906 €	68%	21 372 €	8	Days
QUAREC	ASC	11%	8%	1 211 €	99 €	983 €	10%	842 €	8,5	Days
ACD-T	ASC	81%	81%	2 580 €	2 091 €	2 190 €	95%	6 273 €	3	Days
LACIS-T	ASC	15%	13%	9 661 €	1 227 €	2 190 €	56%	0 €	0	Days
OPAR	OBS	25%	25%	4 543 €	1 144 €	1 000 €	114%	1 144 €	1	Days
SIRTA	OBS	17%	17%	4 334 €	723 €	530 €	136%	15 904 €	22	UWD
RADO	OBS	23%	23%	575 €	130 €	530 €	25%	522 €	4	SWD
CAO	OBS	31%	31%	10 193 €	3 116 €	n/a (actual)		0 €	0	UWD
Average		36%	36%	5 116 €	1 617 €	1 679 €	76%	12 652 €	8	
Minimum		11%	8%	324 €	99 €	530 €	10%	0 €	0	
Maximum		81%	81%	13 132 €	4 220 €	3 906 €	136%	79 947 €	37	
Average ASC		43%	43%	5 233 €	1 811 €	2 274 €	67%	17 372 €	9	
Average OBS		24%	24%	4 911 €	1 278 €	687 €	92%	4 392 €	7	

4.2 Resources required for annual access provision

An RI access programme requires sufficient resources to cover the cost incurred by facilities for providing access. Thanks to the access activities in ATMO-ACCESS, which span a three-year period (from spring 2022 to spring 2025), we have established a reliable basis for assessing the quantity of access provided and, consequently, the needs of the user community in accessing services offered by atmospheric facilities. This experience enables us to estimate the resources required for an average annual access provision, based on a competitive access process (average success rate of 73% throughout seven calls).

In the absence of reliable variable fractions of unit cost for the diverse ATMO-ACCESS facilities, as outlined in the Section 4.1, we propose focusing on the available TNA unit costs within the project. Of the 61 participating facilities, 35 apply a unit access cost, as are listed in Table 2, while the remaining facilities base their access-related expenses on actual costs. Unit costs are available from 21 observational platforms (OBS), nine atmospheric simulation chambers (ASC), four central laboratories (CL), and one mobile platform (MOB). These unit costs vary widely, as illustrated in Figure 5. The average OBS unit cost is approximately 600€ per access unit, with a range from 400€ to 1100€. In contrast, the average ASC unit cost is significantly higher, at 3100€ per access unit, with minimum and maximum values of 1000€ and 6300€, respectively. The average unit cost for the four CL is 800€, ranging from 200€ to 2000€.

Figure 5. Unit costs applied by ATMO-ACCESS facilities

Table 2. Overview of ATMO-ACCESS facilities applying unit cost. Information is provided on the name and type of facility (OBS, ASC, CL, MOB), the country in which they are located, the unit of access applied, the unit cost (A), the estimated quantity of access (B) and estimated access costs (C) in the project. Included are also the actual quantity of access provided within a full 3-year period (2022-2025³, (D), in blue), the inferred average annual values €, as well as the inferred average annual access costs (F).

N°	Facility name	Facility type	CY	Unit of access	Unit cost (€) (A)	Estimated qty of access (B)	Unit Access costs (C)	Actual qty of access (D)	Avg annual qty of access (E)	Avg annual access costs (€) (F)
1	OPAR	OBS	FR	DAY	1 000	160	160 000	119	40	39 667
2	SIRTA-Obs	OBS	FR	UWD	530	277	146 810	301	100	53 177
3	CO-PDD	OBS	FR	UWD	560	250	140 000	48	16	8 960
4	CIAO	OBS	IT	SWD	1 087	138	150 006	106	35	38 407
5	CMN-PV	OBS	IT	UWD	680	220	149 600	113,5	38	25 727
6	MEL	OBS	DE	UWD	666	112	74 592	0	0	0
7	FMI PAL-SOD	OBS	FI	UWD	600	250	150 000	558	186	111 600
8	SMEAR II	OBS	FI	UWD	750	380	285 000	626	209	156 500
9	JFJ	OBS	CH	UWD	800	250	200 000	146	49	38 933
10	CESAR	OBS	NL	UWD	993	151	149 943	384	128	127 104
11	FKL	OBS	GR	UWD	474	210	99 540	186	62	29 388
12	ATMOS	OBS	GR	UWD	470	214	100 580	304	101	47 627
13	PANGEA	OBS	GR	UWD	377	100	37 700	6	2	754
14	RADO	OBS	RO	SWD	530	283	149 990	190	63	33 567
15	ISAF	OBS	ES	SWD	600	116	69 600	102	34	20 400
16	AGORA	OBS	ES	SWD	390	205	79 950	263,5	88	34 255
17	BCN	OBS	ES	UWD	409	110	44 990	120	40	16 360
18	BCN	OBS	ES	UWD	389	90	35 010	48	16	6 224
19	VRS	OBS	DK	UWD	620	64	39 680	124	41	25 627
20	NAOK	OBS	CZ	UWD	690	130	89 700	24	8	5 520
21	ARN	OBS	ES	SWD	471	64	30 144	24	8	3 768
22	CESAM	ASC	FR	DAY	2 100	81	170 100	76	25	53 200
23	HELIOS	ASC	FR	DAY	1 851	54	99 954	22	7	13 574
24	ACD-C / LACIS-T	ASC	DE	DAY	2 190	82	179 580	60	20	43 800
25	SAPHIR/-PLUS	ASC	DE	DAY	6 250	40	250 000	92	31	191 667
26	AIDA	ASC	DE	DAY	5 200	48	249 600	112	37	194 133
27	QUAREC-ASC	ASC	DE	DAY	983	122	119 926	97	32	31 784
28	PACS-C2	ASC	CH	DAY	3 500	71	248 500	120	40	140 000
29	MAC	ASC	UK	DAY	1 500	120	180 000	50	17	25 000
30	EUPHORE	ASC	ES	DAY	3 906	64	249 984	92	31	119 784
31	ICOS ATC	CL	FR	SWD	300	234	70 200	0	0	0
32	WCCAP	CL	DE	SWD	610	65	39 650	32	11	6 507
33	CESAR	CL	NL	SWD	200	750	150 000	567,5	189	37 833
34	ISAF	CL	ES	SWD	2 000	40	80 000	20	7	13 333
35	FCoMLab	MOB	FI	DAY	1 500	50	75 000	0	0	0

³ The values for the quantity of access provided correspond to those certified by March 3, 2025.

The quantity of access provided over the three-year period by unit-cost based facilities, summarised in Table 2, is illustrated in Figure 6. During this time, a total of 5134 access units were provided, with 74% attributed to OBS, 14% to ASC, and 12% to CL. It is important to note that these figures are not representative of the overall access provision in ATMO-ACCESS or by facility type, as facilities operating on actual costs are not included. Additionally, access units vary and should not be directly compared. For instance, the majority (80%) of access provided by OBS corresponds to user-working days (i.e., one user visiting the facility per day), while 18% is measured in DAYs (i.e., a user group, independent of the number of users, visiting per day), and 3% correspond to access units expressed in SWD (i.e., staff-working-days, representing the time facility staff dedicate to access provision). The access units for ASCs are entirely expressed in DAYs, whereas those for CLs are based on SWD).

Figure 6. Breakdown of quantity of access provided by unit costs-based ATMO-ACCESS facilities (2022-2025)

Table 3. Average annual costs of the unit-cost based OBS and ASC facilities in ATMO-ACCESS, calculated from the values listed in Table 2.

Global annual access costs		
	OBS	ASC
N° of facilities	20	9
Annual quantity of access (ATMO-ACCESS)	1264	240
Average annual quantity of access per facility	63 AU ⁴	27 AU
Total annual access cost (ATMO-ACCESS)	823 564 €	812 942 €
Average annual access cost per facility	41 178 €	90 327 €

The resources required for access provision can be calculated based on the annual quantity of access provided (Table 2, column E) and the inferred unit access costs (column F). The three facilities that did not provide any access are excluded from these calculations. The average annual quantity of access per facility over the 3-year period, measured in access units (AU³), is 63 for OBS and 27 for ASC.

⁴ Access unit (AU). For observational facilities (OBS), AU includes UWD (User-Working-Day), SWD (Staff-Working-Day), and DAY. For atmospheric simulation chambers (ASC), AU only denotes DAY.

From the total annual costs of the 20 OBS (accounting for 824 k€) and the 9 ASC (accounting for 813 k€), we can calculate the average annual cost for access provision per facility (Table 3).

The annual access costs per facility are:

- **on average 41.2 k€ per OBS** (for 63 AU, which is the equivalent of about 3-5 user projects⁵) – or 651 € per AU, and
- **on average 90.3 k€ per ASC** (for 27 AU, which also corresponds to about 3-5 users projects⁶) – or 3383 € per AU.

The calculated average OBS and ASC⁷ annual access costs provide an initial basis for estimating the resources required for access provision. This is done by extrapolating the average annual costs as a function of the number of facilities. The estimates are considered robust, as they are based on actual access data collected over the three-year ATMO-ACCESS period. For the analysis, three scenarios were investigated, as indicated in Table 4 and illustrated in Figure 7.

Table 4. Three scenarios of annual access costs calculated as a function of an arbitrary number of facilities considered, based on an average cost of 41 178 € (OBS) and 90 327 € (ASC).

	N° of OBS	Annual OBS Access costs	N° of ASC	Annual ASC Access costs	N° of OBS + ASC	Total annual OBS+ASC Access costs
Scenario S1	3	123 535 €	2	180 654 €	5	304 188 €
Scenario S2	5	205 891 €	5	451 634 €	10	657 525 €
Scenario S3	10	411 782 €	10	903 269 €	20	1 315 050 €

Figure 7 illustrates the average annual access costs as a function of the (arbitrarily selected) number of facilities, highlighting the increasing costs for OBS and ASC as the number of facilities grows, as well as the combined costs when both facility types are included. Additionally, three scenarios are depicted:

- Scenario S1: 5 facilities (3 OBS and 2 ASC),
- Scenario S2: 10 facilities (5 OBS and 5 ASC),
- Scenario S3: 20 facilities (10 OBS and 10 ASC).

⁵ The typical duration of an ATMO-ACCESS user project at an OBS, including 2 users, is about 5 days and translates to 10 UWD.

⁶ The typical duration of an ATMO-ACCESS user project at an ASC, independent of the number of users, is about 5 days, and translates to 5 DAYS.

⁷ The average annual costs for CLs facilities are not calculated, as their units costs vary widely, and most of the participating 13 CLs in the project are based on actual access costs and are not considered here.

For the selected three scenarios, the estimated average annual resources required for access provision are 304 k€, 658 k€, and 1 315 k€, respectively.

Figure 7. Average annual access costs of unit cost-based facilities as a function of calculated average costs and number of facilities considered, and quantity of access provided. The green line indicates the increasing access costs when considering 1 to 20 OBS, whereas the purple line indicates those of ASC increasing from 1 to 15. The grey line indicates the sum of OBS and ASC access costs, indicating the three selected scenarios S1, S2, S3 (the access costs are rounded and given in k€). The red dashed line indicates the limit of access costs at 500 k€.

From the results we can infer that a budget of about 0.5 M€ per year could support access provision by up to 15 facilities, depending on the specific number of OBS or ASC considered. This is further illustrated in Figure 8. For example, an annual budget of around 500 k€ could enable access provision by 12 OBS, or by 6 ASC, or a combination such as 3 OBS and 4 ASC, or 6 OBS and 2 ASC, among other possibilities. It is important to note that these estimates are based on the average real quantity of access delivered over a three-year period in ATMO-ACCESS (2022-2025), with an average of 63 AU (OBS) and 27 AU (ASC) per facility, corresponding

to approximately 3-5 user projects per facility. **The number of facilities could be increased if the number of user projects per facility were reduced to just one or two, which would potentially more than double the number of facilities able to provide access.**

Figure 8. Potential number of facilities (both OBS and ASC) for a given amount of available resources. The number of OBS are indicated as green dots, those of ASC are indicated in purple, while total number of facilities (sum of OBS + ASC) is indicated as blue diamonds. The required resources (± 500 k€) are indicated in pink.

The above results demonstrate that an RI access programme could effectively be implemented with an annual budget of a few hundred k€ (± 0.5 M€), which would enable access provision by a reasonable to substantial number of facilities.

5 Principles and pathways for pricing access

Ensuring long-term access to distributed Research Infrastructures (RIs) requires a diversified funding strategy that integrates multiple financial sources. As outlined in Section 2.1, these sources include national, regional, or institutional funding, project-based funding at both

European and national levels, RI funding through membership contributions, and additional funding such as user or service fees. To support sustainable access, it is essential to develop a pricing scheme that enables a clear calculation of service costs.

The establishment of such a pricing policy relies on a precise assessment of the fraction of costs associated with the access provision, as discussed in Section 4. The pricing scheme should consider different scenarios while ensuring that the costs of providing access are fully covered. Various pricing models should be explored based on the available funding sources, user type (academic vs. non-academic), and user origin (RI member country vs. non-member country). Pricing should remain flexible and account for the possibility of subsidised access for users, e.g., from RI member countries. By adopting a balanced and adaptable approach, the introduction of a pricing scheme will enhance the financial sustainability of RIs while ensuring fair and efficient access to their services.

5.1 Principles for pricing policy

A well-structured and robust pricing framework for service access should be guided by key principles that balance cost recovery with flexibility, fairness, and transparency.

- **Cost coverage and sustainability** must be a central consideration. The pricing model should reflect the real costs associated with providing access to RI services, including operational expenses, maintenance, and administrative overheads. This ensures that RIs remain financially viable in the long term without creating an undue financial burden on users.
- **Flexibility in pricing** is crucial to accommodate different user categories and funding conditions (Figure 8). Various user scenarios and funding mechanisms should be taken into account, including academic and non-academic users, and users from RI member countries versus external users. A tiered pricing structure should consider for instance subsidised access offered to certain users, particularly those originating from RI member countries and engaged in publicly funded or collaborative research.
- **Transparency and fairness** should underpin the pricing policy. Clearly defined cost structures and access conditions help users understand the rationale behind pricing decisions and foster trust in the RI's financial model. This also includes ensuring that the pricing scheme aligns with the different funding mechanisms, including EU transnational access schemes or project-based grants, where applicable.

- **Open science principles and knowledge dissemination** should be encouraged through pricing incentives. Waived or subsidised service fees should require users to making their research outputs publicly available, supporting the broader scientific community and reinforcing the role of RIs as enablers of open science. Conversely, proprietary or commercial research may be subject to full-cost pricing, reflecting the exclusive nature of such access.
- **Periodic evaluation and adaptability** are essential to maintaining a pricing policy that evolves with changing financial and research landscapes. Regular assessment of access costs, user demand, and funding availability will allow for adjustments to ensure continued accessibility and sustainability.

By adhering to these principles, a well-designed pricing policy can balance financial responsibility with equitable access, fostering long-term sustainability for RIs while supporting a diverse user community.

Figure 9. Service fees as a function of cost coverage. User fees for access to services are waived if the costs of access provision are fully covered by an external funding source (e.g., EU INFRA-SERV or RI funding). A reduced fee may apply if a minimum amount of cost sharing by the users is needed. Otherwise, full costs are charged to users.

5.2 Funding pathways for users

To establish an RI pricing policy, it is crucial to have accurate information on the real costs associated with providing access. This information enables the establishment of appropriate service fees for each of the RI services offered. As services within an RI are typically provided under a unified framework, user requests are centrally managed through a single entry point. These requests then undergo a harmonised access process, which is generally competitive in nature. Figure 10 illustrates a potential funding pathway to cover the access costs, considering the availability of multiple funding sources.

Figure 10. Possible RI user funding pathway in case of multiple access funding sources. In all cases, the access process is competitive, requiring an application and selection process as for example implemented within ATMO-ACCESS (exceptions may apply in the case of private sector users).

- (1) **Waived or subsidised user fees** may be applicable when a coordinated RI access programme is in place. Such access, whether free-of-charge or at reduced rates, is generally available only to users from RI member or observer countries. This access is governed by the RI's access and policies and management plans (R2). Typically, it involves a competitive selection process and includes user obligations, such as the provision of open access to results and publications following the access. The user selection process ensures that the access remains equitable and follows established guidelines.
- (2) **Free access** to RI services is possible only if funding sources are available to cover the costs incurred by the facility in providing access. A typical example of this funding mechanism is EU INFRA-SERV projects, which allow facilities to recover some of the necessary resources as part of a harmonised and competitive access process (R3). Within this framework, the eligibility of users is determined following the demand for access, which is assessed based on scientific excellence criteria. Users must also commit to providing open access to the results and publications that arise from the access. While there are minimal constraints regarding the type of user (academic or non-academic),

their professional profile (expert or early-career), or their geographic origin (European or international), the access must be transnational. Furthermore, the participation of international users is generally capped at 20% of the total user base. Costs reimbursed to facilities are based on previously agreed-upon unit costs (as detailed in 4.2).

- (3) **Subsidised user fees**, either fully or partially waived, may apply in case where agreements are in place to partially or fully cover the costs of access. The specific conditions for these subsidies depend on the agreements between the parties involved. Examples of such agreements could include the Italian project [ITINERIS](#) or the ECMWF-CAMS (European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts - Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service) contracts, as outlined in Section 2.1. These arrangements help ensure that access remains affordable for users, while also ensuring that facilities are reimbursed for the resources they expend.
- (4) **Full access fees** apply when there is no external funding available to subsidise or waive the costs. This scenario may apply to specific users, such as those from the private sector, who may seek access to RI services for proprietary research. For industrial users, there are no obligations to provide open access to the research results generated through the access. These users are required to adhere to the overall access process established by the RI, although there may be some flexibility or exceptions, such as bypassing the peer-review step.

6 Conclusions

Ensuring sustainable access to distributed RIs requires a robust financial framework that balances diverse sources funding while maintaining broad user accessibility to its services. This study explores various funding mechanisms, including national/regional/institutional funding, project-based contributions, RI funding, and service fees, to identify optimal cost models and pricing strategies for atmospheric RI services. The initial objective was to conduct a comprehensive cost analysis across a representative set of ATMO-ACCESS facilities, using a full-cost approach that distinguishes between fixed and variable costs of access provision. The aim was to determine the real costs directly associated with service provision and develop a tiered pricing scheme that ensures full cost recovery, integrating an RI access programme as well as potential service fees as potential funding mechanisms.

Although the collected data remain incomplete for developing a comprehensive cost model, the results suggest that the TNA unit cost approach serves as a reasonable approximation when detailed variable cost data are unavailable. Based on three-year access data provided within the project, it is possible to estimate the annual resources required to sustain physical and remote access, and demonstrate the viability of considering an RI access programme. Results demonstrate the feasibility of implementing an access programme, enabling access provision by considerable number of facilities with a given budget of around half a million €.

Aligning funding strategies with European and national research priorities, leveraging project-based funding, and optimizing financial mechanisms will be crucial for ensuring the long-term sustainability of RI services. A structured pricing policy, guided by principles of cost coverage, transparency, and flexibility, will be essential. Financial sustainability relies on a precise knowledge of the access costs. The pricing scheme should account for different scenarios while ensuring that the costs of providing access are covered through available funding sources. Differentiated pricing models, tailored to user categories and service types, offer a viable approach to cost recovery without compromising the scientific excellence and open-access principles of distributed atmospheric RIs.

7 Reference documents

Reference N°	Description / Link
R1	ATMO-ACCESS Milestone 3 - Report on access cost case studies at selected facilities (Internal report)
R2	ATMO-ACCESS D1.2 - Consolidation of access policies and legal framework for atmospheric research infrastructures. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13912849 .
R3	ATMO-ACCESS Deliverable D1.1 – Report proposing a common access management concept for atmospheric RIs. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13912804 .

Annex A. Overview of European ERICs and access funding

Table A1.1. Overview of European ERICs and other RIs and their funding of physical access (PA) and remote access (RA). VA denotes virtual access. The RI's main scientific fields are Data, Computing & Digital (DCI), Energy (ENE), Environment (ENV), Health & Food (H&F), Physical Sciences and Engineering (PSE), Social & Cultural Innovation (SCI). RIs are either distributed (D) or single-sited, their lifecycle comprises preparation (P), implementation (I) and/or operation (O) phases. RIs on the ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures) roadmap have either project (P) or Landmark (L) status. The asterisk () denotes information on PA and RA funding which was derived from publicly available sources and may contain inaccuracies.*

#	RI Name	Title	ERIC Establishment	Main Scient Field	RI Type	RI Lifecycle Phase	ESFRI Status (year)	Services types	Access Type	PA/RA Funding*				
										RI	EU INFRA	Service / User	Nat / Oth	
ERICs														
1	<u>ACTRIS ERIC</u>	Aerosol, Clouds, Trace gases RI	2023	ENV	D	I+O	P (2016) L (2021)	Atmospheric observational and exploratory facilities and data for academic research	PA/RA/VA		x			
2	<u>ANAEE ERIC</u>	Analysis and Experimentation on Ecosystems	2022	H&F	D	O	P (2010) L (2021)	Experimental platforms for ecosystem research to understand the impact of climate change	PA/RA/VA		x			
3	<u>BBMRI ERIC</u>	Biobanking and BioMolecular Resources RI	2014	H&F	D	O	P (2006) L (2016)	Quality-controlled human biological samples and associated data for research purposes	PA/RA/VA	x	x	x		

#	RI Name	Title	ERIC Establishment	Main Scient Field	RI Type	RI Lifecycle Phase	ESFRI Status (year)	Services types	Access Type	PA/RA Funding*			
										RI	EU INFRA	Service / User	Nat / Oth
4	CERIC-ERIC	Central European RI Consortium	2014	PSE	D	O		Integrated multidisciplinary facilities for materials and biomaterials research	PA/RA/VA	x	x		x
5	CESSDA ERIC	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives	2017	SCI	D	O	P (2006) L (2016)	Large-scale, integrated, and sustainable data services to the social sciences	VA				
6	CLARIN ERIC	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure	2012	SCI	D	O	P (2006) L (2016)	Digital language resources, data and advanced tools	VA				
7	DARIAH ERIC	Digital RI for the Arts and Humanities	2014	SCI	D	O	P (2006) L (2016)	Digitally-enabled research and teaching across the arts and humanities	VA				
8	EATRIS ERIC	European Advanced Translational RI in Medicine	2013	H&F	D	O	P (2006) L (2016)	High-quality services to the biomedical research community	PA/RA/VA		x	x	
9	ECCSEL ERIC	European Carbon Dioxide Capture and Storage Laboratory Infrastructure	2017	ENE	D	I+O	P (2008) L (2018)	Facilities for carbon capture and storage research	PA/RA/VA		x	x	
10	ECRIN ERIC	European Clinical RI Network	2013	H&F	D	O	P (2006) L (2016)	infrastructure and services for multinational clinical	PA/RA/VA		x		x

#	RI Name	Title	ERIC Establishment	Main Scient Field	RI Type	RI Lifecycle Phase	ESFRI Status (year)	Services types	Access Type	PA/RA Funding*			
										RI	EU INFRA	Service / User	Nat / Oth
								research projects in Europe					
11	<u>ELI ERIC</u>	Extreme Light Infrastructure	2021	PSE	S	I	P (2006) L (2016)	Facilities for high-power, high-intensity laser research	PA/RA/VA	x	x	x	
12	<u>EMBRC ERIC</u>	European Marine Biological Resource Centre	2018	H&F	D	O	P (2008) L (2018)	Fundamental and applied research in marine biology and ecology	PA/RA/VA		x	x	
13	<u>EMSO ERIC</u>	European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and Water Column Observatory	2016	ENV	D	O	P (2006) L (2016)	Ocean observatories for climate and geohazard monitoring	PA/RA/VA		x	x	x
14	<u>EPOS ERIC</u>	European Plate Observing System	2018	ENV	D	O	P (2008) L (2018)	Integrating research infrastructures for solid Earth science in Europe	PA/RA/VA		x	x	
15	<u>ESS ERIC</u>	European Spallation source	2015	PSE	S	I+O	P (2006) L (2016)	Multi-disciplinary research facility based on the world's most powerful neutron source	PA/RA/VA	x	x	x	x
16	<u>ESS ERIC</u>	European Social Survey	2013	SCI	D	O	P (2006) L (2016)	Surveys for measuring EU attitudes, beliefs, behavior patterns of diverse populations in	VA				

#	RI Name	Title	ERIC Establishment	Main Scient Field	RI Type	RI Lifecycle Phase	ESFRI Status (year)	Services types	Access Type	PA/RA Funding*			
										RI	EU INFRA	Service / User	Nat / Oth
17	<u>EURO-ARGO ERIC</u>	European contribution to the international Argo Programme	2014	ENV	D	O	P (2006) L (2016)	Worldwide array of 3500 autonomous instruments on subsurface ocean properties	VA				
18	<u>EU-OPENSREEN ERIC</u>	European Infrastructure of Open Screening Platforms for Chemical Biology	2018	H&F	D	O	P (2008) L (2018)	Distributed network of screening platforms for chemical biology	PA/RA/VA		x		x
19	<u>Euro-Biolmaging ERIC</u>	European Rfor Imaging Technologies in Biological and Biomedical Sciences	2019	H&F	D	O	P (2008) L (2018)	Advanced imaging facilities and technologies for life scientists	PA/RA/VA	x	x	x	x
20	<u>EU-SOLARIS ERIC</u>	European SOLAR Rfor Concentrated Solar Power	2022	ENE	D	O	P (2010) L (2021)	Solar power facilities supporting research in concentrated solar thermal energy	PA/RA/VA	x	x	x	
21	<u>ICOS ERIC</u>	Integrated Carbon Observation System	2015	ENV	D	O	P (2006) L (2016)	Monitoring greenhouse gases through integrated, long-term observations across EU	VA				
22	<u>INFRAFRONTIER</u>	European RI for Modelling Human Diseases	2023	H&F	D	O		Biomedical research facilities and services to explore human diseases	PA/RA/VA	x	x	x	

#	RI Name	Title	ERIC Establishment	Main Scient Field	RI Type	RI Lifecycle Phase	ESFRI Status (year)	Services types	Access Type	PA/RA Funding*			
										RI	EU INFRA	Service / User	Nat / Oth
23	<u>INSTRUCT ERIC</u>	Integrated Structural Biology RI	2017	H&F	D	O	P (2006) L (2016)	High-end technologies and methods in structural biology	PA/RA/VA	x	x	x	
24	<u>JIV ERIC</u>	Joint Institute for VLBI - Very Long Baseline Interferometry	2014	PSE	D	O		European VLBI Telescope Network for radio astronomy	PA/RA/VA		x	x	x
25	<u>LifeWatch ERIC</u>	e-Science and Technology European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research	2017	ENV	D	O	P (2006) L (2016)	e-Science research facilities for biodiversity data and ecosystem research	VA				
26	<u>LOFAR</u>	Low Frequency ARray distributed RI	2023	PSE	D	I+O		European network of LOFAR radio telescopes	PA/RA/VA		x		x
27	<u>MIRRI ERIC</u>	Microbial Resource RI	2022	H&F	D	I+O	P (2010) L (2021)	Microbial Resources and services to support research and development	PA/RA/VA		x		
28	<u>SHARE ERIC</u>	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe	2011	SCI	D	O	P (2006) L (2016)	Multidisciplinary microdata on health, socio-economic status, social and family networks of individuals aged 50+	VA				
Other Ris													

#	RI Name	Title	ERIC Establishment	Main Scient Field	RI Type	RI Lifecycle Phase	ESFRI Status (year)	Services types	Access Type	PA/RA Funding*			
										RI	EU INFRA	Service / User	Nat / Oth
29	<u>DANUBIUS</u>	Interdisciplinary research and innovation on River-Sea Systems		ENV	D	I+O	P (2016)	Interdisciplinary research and innovation on River-Sea Systems	PA/RA/VA		x		
30	<u>DiSSCo</u>	Distributed System of Scientific Collections		ENV	D	I+O	P (2018)	Natural science collections for data-intensive research and innovation in environment, food security, health, and bioeconomy	VA				
31	<u>ECORD</u>	European Consortium for Ocean Research Drilling		ENV	D	O	-	European Consortium for Ocean Research Drilling	PA/RA/VA				
32	<u>EIRENE</u>	Environmental Exposure Assessment RI		H&F	D	P	P (2021)	Environmental Exposure Assessment RI services for chemical profiling, env samples & data, toxicological profiling, biological profiling	PA/RA/VA		x		
33	<u>EISCAT 3D</u>	Next generation European Incoherent Scatter radar system		ENV	S	I+O	P (2008) L (2018)	Next generation European Incoherent Scatter radar system	PA/RA/VA	x		x	x
34	<u>ELIXIR</u>	Distributed infrastructure for life-science information		H&F	D	O	P (2006) L (2016)	Distributed infrastructure for life-science information	VA				

#	RI Name	Title	ERIC Establishment	Main Scient Field	RI Type	RI Lifecycle Phase	ESFRI Status (year)	Services types	Access Type	PA/RA Funding*			
										RI	EU INFRA	Service / User	Nat / Oth
35	<u>eLTER</u>	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological system Research Infrastructure		ENV	D	I	P (2018)	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological system RI	PA/RA/VA		x		
36	<u>EMPHASIS</u>	European Infrastructure for Multi-scale Plant Phenomics and Simulation		H&F	D	O	P (2016)	European Infrastructure for Multi-scale Plant Phenomics and Simulation	PA/RA/VA		x		
37	<u>ERIGrid</u>	European RIsupporting Smart Grid Systems Technology Development		ENE	D	O	-	European RIsupporting Smart Grid Systems Technology Development	PA/RA/VA		x		
38	<u>EUFAR AISBL</u>	European Facility For Airborne Research		ENV	D	O	-	European Facility For Airborne Research	PA/RA/VA				x
39	<u>INTERACT</u>	International Network for Research and Monitoring in the Arctic		ENV	D		-	International Network for Research and Monitoring in the Arctic	PA/RA/VA		x		
40	<u>IBISBA-Bio2E</u>	European Industrial Biotechnology Innovation and Synthetic Biology Accelerator		H&F	D	I	P (2018)	European Industrial Biotechnology Innovation and Synthetic Biology Accelerator	VA				

#	RI Name	Title	ERIC Establishment	Main Scient Field	RI Type	RI Lifecycle Phase	ESFRI Status (year)	Services types	Access Type	PA/RA Funding*			
										RI	EU INFRA	Service / User	Nat / Oth
41	<u>IAGOS AISBL</u>	In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System		ENV	D	O	P (2006) L (2016)	In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System	VA				
42	<u>JERICO</u>	European Coastal Ocean Observing System		ENV	D		-	European Coastal Ocean Observing System	PA/RA/VA		x		
43	<u>Laserlab-Europe AISBL</u>	Consortium of European Laser Ris		PSE	D		-	Consortium of European Laser Ris	PA/RA/VA	x	x		x
44	<u>METROFOOD</u>	Infrastructure for Promoting Metrology in Food and Nutrition		H&F	D	I+O	P (2018)	Infrastructure for Promoting Metrology in Food and Nutrition	PA/RA/VA		x		
45	<u>NEP</u>	European Nanoscience Consortium Pilot		PSE	D			European Nanoscience Consortium Pilot	PA/RA/VA		x		
46	<u>OPR</u>	OPTICON RAdioNet Pilot		PSE	D		-	OPTICON RAdioNet Pilot	PA/RA/VA		x		x
47	<u>PRACE</u>	Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe		DCI	D	I	P (2006) L (2016)	Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe	VA				
48	<u>SIOS</u>	Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System		ENV	D	O	-	International observing system for long-term measurements in and around the Norwegian archipelago of Svalbard	PA/RA/VA	x	x		x

Annex B. Design of the access cost collector tool and guidelines for data collection

B.1 Access cost collector tool

The access cost collector tool, developed in Excel, is used to collect from the different ATMO-ACCESS facilities (see Figure B1.1). The tool captures details on costs categories and types (figure B1.2), units of access, and the quantity of access provided (Figure B1.2).

PLATFORM INFORMATION						
Country	Platform type	Platform name	Platform short name	Platform PI		N° of host institutions
				Name	e-mail	Short name of platform's host institution(s)
select...	select...					0
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: fit-content;"><p>Need to select ATMO-ACCESS platforms:</p><ul style="list-style-type: none">• OBS• ASC• MOB• CL</div>						

Figure B1.1. Collection of Information on type of facility: Observational platform (OBS), Atmospheric simulation chamber (ASC), Mobile platform (MOB), Central laboratory (CL).

B.2 Guidelines for data collection using the cost collector tool

Guidelines were provided for the use of the cost collector tool, explaining the perimeter of costs to include, information on cost categories and types, type, unit and quantity of access and user origin.

Guidelines for collecting the costs of access to services provided by ATMO-ACCESS facilities using the cost collector tool

1- Introduction

This cost collector tool aims at collecting information on operation costs at ATMO-ACCESS facilities related to the access of users to the services provided by the facility.

The aim of the exercise is to be able to determine the full costs of access for the facilities, to be used as a basis for elaborating a sustainable access cost model for the research infrastructure.

2- Perimeter

The access costs are related to specific service types provided by the facility which comprise: research services, technical services, training services, innovation services, and data services.

The provision of services is measured based on units of access (section 3), which must be defined for each service type indicated above. Each facility should at least complete one cost collector per facility. If the unit of access and costs per unit of access between the service types differ, then more than one cost collector should be used (although avoided if possible). A facility may offer different services without the need to define different access costs.

3- Access cost information

3.1 General access cost information

The access costs to be collected for each facility comprise all expenses incurred each year in the reference period 2019-2022. The costs must be provided in euros.

The costs should be provided by the access provider, according to the recorded accounts of the host institution(s) operating the facility, and in line with their usual accounting practices. In case several host institutions are involved, the costs should be separated. Thus, the underlying costs should be based on historical (auditable) data, where available. Estimates should be avoided as best as possible.

3.2 Cost categories

Access costs comprise all operating costs incurred by a facility for providing a service to users. The costs categories include:

- **Personnel costs:** e.g., of technical and scientific personnel directly assigned to the planning, preparation, and functioning of the facility for the provision of access (before, during, and after) and to support the users with training, scientific expertise, and other on-site needs; of personnel for administrative support and logistics (including customs, shipping and transport of instrumentation, arrangements of travel and accommodation, etc.).
- **Equipment costs:** for capital investments needed to provide access to users and having a minimum useful lifetime, e.g., scientific and technical instrumentation, buildings and facility space, vehicles, furniture, or similar. Equipment costs are expressed as depreciation costs to consider the decrease of the value of the equipment based on its useful lifetime. Therefore, they require information on the purchase price and date of the equipment. The effects of inflation will be considered and can be disregarded at this stage.
- **Other costs:** include consumables costs for the provision of services (e.g. technical gases, chemicals, filters, tools and small consumable items, spare parts, other maintenance and repair costs, computing and communication costs, etc.), travel costs of facility staff for the provision of services, transport costs of any equipment needed by the access provider to deliver the services. Note that travel costs of users are not eligible.
- **Indirect costs:** are access costs that are not directly traceable to the provision to services. However, they are essential for a full cost calculation and must be identified and accounted. Indirect costs can include, e.g., space rental, utilities (water, electricity, gas, internet, etc.), general administration, accounting and legal expenses, general expenses for office, security, computing, data processing, cleaning, telephone, costs for maintenance and insurance, or other expenses. The apportionment of indirect costs is done following a defined calculation key according to the accounting rules of the hosting institution(s) and may, therefore, vary (i.e., some institutions may consider direct costs which are indirect costs for others, and vice versa).

3.3 Fixed and variable costs

For the future cost model, information about fixed and variable access costs are very relevant:

- **Fixed costs:** the costs for operating the facilities remain unchanged over a period of time whatever the quantity of access provided is. When the quantity of access increases, the fixed costs do not change. Fixed costs can comprise both, direct and indirect costs (see examples in Figure 1).

- **Variable costs** change when the quantity of access changes. When the quantity of access provided increases, the variable costs increase as well, and vice versa. Variable costs can comprise both, direct and indirect costs (Fig. A1.4).

The ratio of fixed vs variable costs should be indicated as a percentage and be estimated as best as possible based on the cost item and the quantity of access provided for the period.

Figure A1.4. Examples of fixed and variable costs for both direct and indirect costs in relation to access provision.

4- Type, unit and quantity of access

4.1 Type of access

Access can be physical, remote, hybrid, or virtual.

- **Physical access:** "hands-on" access of a user who physically visits a facility. Access is made to resources that are not unlimited, therefore, the access is based on a competitive selection process.
- **Remote access:** access to a facility without user's) physically visiting the facility. Access is made to resources that are not unlimited, therefore, the access is based on a competitive selection process.
- **Hybrid access:** a combination of physical and remote access.
- **Virtual access:** wide and free access of users to services through communication networks. Access can be made simultaneously by an unlimited number of users, without selection.

4.2 Unit of access

Access units are a measure allowing to quantify the amount of access provided.

The unit of access should be defined for each service. There is no need for one coherent access unit. However, as access costs are defined on the basis of the access units defined, a minimum amount of coherence / simplification should be sought. Examples are:

- **Staff-working-day (SWD) or staff-working-hour (SWH)** = equivalence of one labour day (hour) required by the facility staff person to provide the access to the services
- **User-working-day (UWD)** = equivalence of one working day spent by one user at the facility to access the services
- **Day (DAY)** = equivalence of one working day spent by one or several users at the facility to use its services, independent of the number of users
- **Other** → one service provided (e.g., one calibration, one data processing service)

4.3 Quantity of access

The quantity of access is an indicator of the service provision by the facility. The quantity of access should be given based on the defined unit of access for the service at the facility (UWD, DAY, SWD, ...) and for each access type (physical, remote, hybrid, virtual access).

5- User's country of origin

For the quantity of access indicated in the reference period, an estimation of the countries of origin should be given on a broad scale:

- Percentage of **European users**: refers to those users affiliated to an institution from any of the European member, associated and candidate countries. If available: indicate the percentage of users coming from European countries but not belonging to the RI (indicate country(ies) concerned).
- Percentage of **international users**: refers to users affiliated to institutions based in countries outside the European member, associated and candidate countries.
- Percentage of **national users**: refers to users affiliated to an institution based in the country where the facility is located (excluding internal users).
- Percentage of **internal users**: refers to users affiliated with the hosting institution(s) of the facility.

The sum of all user types should add up to 100%.